

STYLISTIC–FOREGROUNDING IN PRESIDENT BOLA TINUBU’S FIRST DEMOCRACY DAY SPEECH, ON JUNE 12, 2023

OKUGBE, Monday Afeakhare (Ph.D)
&
Dr. (MRS) EDOKPAY, Justina
Department of English, Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State

Abstract

The study investigates the Stylistic- foregrounding features of President Bola Tinubu’s First Speech, to address Nigerians on the occasion of June 12, 2023 democracy day remembrance. In the study, the procedure of stylistic approach is adopted to examine how the president’s deployment of language devices in his address deepens communication, and distinguishes him as a democrat, to enable him demonstrate his readiness to provide good governance to Nigerians. Therefore, the study focuses on the functional features that characterize his speech, by attempting to reveal that his administration is ready to make significant contributions or landmarks to the re-building and development of Nigeria through the process of democracy by the observance of due process. To that end, the study recommends that appropriate attention should be paid to language peculiarities in the President’s speech, which are not only aimed at commemorating the enduring nascent democratic practice in Nigeria, but also at sensitizing and educating the public on the essence of democracy, which the election of MKO Abiola on June 12, 1993, the adjudged Nigeria’s freest and fairest elections represents.

Keywords: Stylistic-foregrounding, President Bola Tinubu, Democracy day, governance, building and development.

Introduction

We can aptly situate President Bola Tinubu’s First Speech to address Nigerians on the occasion of June 12, 2023 democracy day remembrance as language of politics. Ideally, success or failure of any political office holder does not only depend on how good or bad his policies, political ideologies and programmes are, but to a large extent, good and effective communication with the people being governed constitute the bedrock of a good administration, involving the ability to manipulate the resources of language in order to carry the people along in the course of executing government’s programmes. (Joseph Alagbe 42). Similarly, Abiola Kalejaiye opines that language and politics are obviously connected. He states that politics is concerned with the power to make decisions, to influence resources, direct other people’s behaviour, as well as their values and desires, while language on its part, is an instrument of power in the hands of democratic leaders (645).

From the foregoing, it is obvious that language and politics are interconnected; language is, for instance, considered the vehicular expression of politics. It is the means by which politics or political discourse and ideas are widely disseminated. (Kalejaiye 200). This shows that language is the most important point of entry into habits of thought of a people since it embodies within

itself cumulative association derived from the total experiences of its people. What this implies is that every political authority will lead to justify itself by an appeal to language in its symbolic or realistic sense. It is apparent from the various opinions stated above that language is the key factor in political behaviour concerning mobilizing people for support and acceptance; it is this relatedness of language and politics that justifies the need for this study to investigate the employment of Stylistic - Foregrounding in President Bola Tinubu's Democracy Day Celebration Speech, in order to identify and examine the features inherent in the language of the political leader which show relatedness to the contextual message

Democracy Day Remembrance is now celebrated as an annual event; set aside to commemorate the democratic election of MKO Abiola on June 12, 1993, which has been adjudged Nigeria's freest and fairest election. Though Presidential addresses are common events associated with political discourse by past and present Presidents of Nigeria, the Federal government had recently acknowledged Democracy Day formally, as a miles stone in the history of Nigerian politics, considering reference to it as a turning point in the growth and development of Nigerian politics. Hence, the examination of stylistic- foregrounding in Bola Tinubu's Speech is apt in this study, which is anchored on MAK Halliday's systemic functional linguistics.

2. Theoretical Background/Analytical Method

The systemic functional linguistics is adopted to investigate this study. It is a linguistic approach which considers not only the structure of the language, but also its social context. According to Liu Zhengyuan, the application of Systemic Functional Model in the analysis of multimodal discourse is related to the theoretical and practical meaning extraction from the data, to show multiple semiotic resources in textual, printed and electronic texts, including to visual language. This implies that, for us to derive the total meaning of any text, there must be formal and semantic interaction (Anne Cluysenaar19).

In this paper, therefore, stylistic- foregrounding features in President Tinubu's speech are studied from the levels of graphology, syntax and lexico-semantics in order to offer us a very systematic insight of exploring the patterns the speech builds from the material of language to make meaning. Since foregrounding is a key concept in stylistics in the field of linguistics, it involves the use of linguistic devices to underscore certain elements in a text, making them to stand out, or 'foregrounded.' Foregrounding can create effects, such as surprise, focus, or emphasis in a text (Ayo Ogunsiji 123). It is our belief that the meaning a speech elicits is reinforced by language choices at those levels. However, Asonwan Adagbonyin states that it does not imply that each level of language use is autonomous; but the language features are inter-levels reinforcing and complement other levels, thus confirming the text as a discourse (143). By identifying and describing these important patterns of language in the text, we focus on both the formal and functional dimensions of language use, with emphasis on communicative function. This approach underscores the deep social concerns of the text, suggesting that the text is a product of social situations, and implying that there is a common relationship between language use and situations.

The dominant techniques deployed to create foregrounding in the president's speech include: graphological style, pattern repetition, figurative language, parallelism and lexical neologism and allusion.

3 Textual Analysis and Discussions

In this section, attention is paid to the analytical organization and discussions of President Bola Tinubu's First Democracy Day Speech, delivered on 12th June, 2023. The stylistic-foregrounding resources in the Speech are presented through the features of graphology, pattern repetition/parallelism, figurative language and diction, in order to enhance clarity and understanding of his message, as follows:

a. Graphological patterns

Graphology is defined as the study of graphemes and other features associated with the written medium, such as punctuation, paragraphing, or spacing (Katie Wales 182). According to Geoffrey Leech, graphology is "the line-by-line arrangement of words on the printed page" (68). In their contribution to what graphology is all about, Crystal and Davy note that graphology is the analogous study of language writing system or orthography and typography (18). This means that graphology has to do with a writer's style. President Tinubu largely foregrounds some graphic resources in his speech to portray his attempt to give a comprehensive reports of some critical national issues, including the democratization process and the electoral reforms in Nigeria.

Obviously, the Speech layout is fore grounded with the graphological resource of point by point itemization, graphically represented with items number 1 to 25, thereby replacing the conventional paragraphing pattern of a narrative. The itemized points are rendered in a crescendo to enable the president, vividly unfold the series of events that had resulted in the growth of democracy in Nigeria. The strategy of itemizing is not only enterprising, it is also an explicit way of creating room for orderly presentation of ideas intended in the message being delivered, with clarity in three phases or sections, in such a manner that section one employs a nominal phrase, as follows:

Extract I

Fellow Nigerians, (item 1)

The above extract represents a foregrounded graphological marker in President Tinubu's Speech, deployed to convey his expression of love for the people he governs, his humility, respect and readiness to listen and serve Nigerians. The phrase also stand out distinct to salute the people and create a sense of fondness and bond; unity and solidarity; which he attempts to share with Nigerians. This is consciously done to usher in a good environment that would enable him deliver 'the dividends of democracy'.

Also, the second section of the president's speech, which ranges from items 2-12, marks out the ugly past of Nigerian political history, as characterized by oppressive military dictatorship, infringement on fundamental human rights and massive corruption, associated with the military regime, which motivate the birth of democracy.

The final section, as contained in items 13-25 foregrounds the president's economic and social blue print, proposed in his administration. Each of these three sections is replete with foregrounded graphological features that underscore

the president's determined wish to make a difference in governance, conveyed through the choice of appropriate language devices shown below.

b. Lexico –Semantic Features

Lexico-semantic features expose the meaning of the words and syntax in utterances, and how the elements of the sentence come together in the interpretation of the text. At this level of analysis, emphasis is placed on the derivable meaning of expressions, irrespective of their lexical composition. Such expressions must show the relationship between the referent and the reference, aimed at making the message clear, simple, convincing and unambiguous. Through figurative language, we shall explore the special uses into which President Tinubu puts certain lexical items, and their contributions to his message.

Figurative language involves transfer of meaning through analogy. It is a way of saying something other than the ordinary way in order to achieve special meaning. This is a common practice among speakers, whereby African speakers deviate from the rules of English grammar in form of figurative use of language, aimed at flavouring their expressions. President Tinubu, in his speech, makes profuse use of figures of speech to create special meanings and reflect Nigerian situation, in such figures as:

Simile

In its general sense, a simile is a linguistic expression, which compares two entities. It involves the comparison between two different entities or events. It is identified with the use of direct comparison, introduced by 'like' and 'as'. Simile is dominantly used for clarification and description of events in the speech as follows:

Extract 2

- i. Just like the anti-colonial movement, the pro-june 12 vanguard demonstrated, once again, the enduring validity of the 19th century historian Arnold Toynbee's eternal postulation, that civilization and societies experience progress....(item 5).
- ii. ... guide it and protect it like a precious jewel (item 9).

In sample i of the above extract, President Tinubu likens the efforts it took Nigerians to earn the present democratic practice to that of the difficulties encountered before Nigeria could get its independence from foreign domination, a situation which according to him, has validated the legend's (Arnold Toynbee) assertion, implying that democracy is associated with modern civilization, progress and the best global practice in governance, which has stood the test time.

In sample ii, the president, through the use of simile, buttresses the excellent practice of good governance in Nigeria through democracy, being the best global option to be embraced.

Metaphor

According to John Lyons, metaphor is a figure of speech dealing with a kind of transference of meaning through an analogy, involving two things being directly compared (52). Metaphoric language implies comparison of one sort of element, quality or action to another without stating the exact relation between them, and without using 'like' and 'as'. (Udofot and Basse 80). Metaphor reflects cultural meanings in language, and can also assist in understanding the thought patterns and beliefs of an entire social group. This implies bringing two different concepts together

in a linguistic expression that rouses some meaningful transfer of sense in interpretation. Generally, writers employ metaphors to convey intended meanings and give potency to the ideational function of language. Social meanings contained in metaphor of a particular language embody the culture of its owners (the native speakers of such language). In Nigeria, metaphors are used to relate Nigerian experiences and contexts. This is succinctly foregrounded in the president's speech as shown below.

Extract 3

. . . . The substantial number of our people who participated in the **struggle to de-annul the election** signified **their fierce commitment** . . . **fierce opposition** . . . unrelenting **pro- democracy onslaught** . . . the equivalent of **the battle against colonial rule** . . . (item 4).

The above extract is highly figurative. Specifically, it reflects the metaphoric picture used by the speaker to capture how all Nigerians fought tooth and nail against the post colonial agents (the military government), as well as the colonial powers. The foregrounded features of “**struggle, fierce, onslaught and battle**” capture the speaker's explicit reminiscences about the country's earlier unfortunate, oppressive and ugly political happenings, which some patriotic Nigerians fought against with a sense of commitment and sacrifices, thereby motivating celebration of democracy in the president's speech.

Transferred Epithet

Transferred epithet refers to the act of transferring an adjective usually used to describe one thing, to another. This involves adjectives being transferred to a different noun as foregrounded below.

Extract 4

i. In rising to strongly oppose the arbitrary annulment of **the will of the majority** of Nigerians (item 4).

ii They gave their yesterday for the liberty that is ours today (item 8).

In sample i of the above extract, the president describes the 1993 General Presidential Election, which is believed to be fairest and freest as “**the will of the majority**”. The transfer of ‘will’ as a term to account for ‘the public acceptability of the election results’ is suggestive of the importance the president places on genuine election results in a democratic government. In sample ii of the extract, the president similarly extols the qualities of valour and patriotism displayed by those who died to achieve democracy in Nigeria. The choice of language in the extract reflects his criticism and hatred for the annulment of June 12 election results that were never declared by the military regime.

Personification

This is another figurative device utilized in the president's text. The strategy involves representing objects, qualities and non-human beings as humans. Ideas or objects so personified are semantically foregrounded. The rules of semantic expectancy are violated in personification. This device is effectively used by President Tinubu to animate his feelings and inner thoughts, in order to arouse readers' emotion and foreground the object of his description as shown below.

Extract 5

The **abortion**, by military fiat of the decisive victory of Chief Moshood Abiola ... turned out to be the seed that germinated into the prolonged struggle **that gave birth to the democracy** we currently enjoy ...(item 3).

In the above extract, “The **abortion**” ... of the decisive victory turned out to be the seed that germinated into the prolonged struggle “**that gave birth to democracy**”, characterize personified expressions with human attributes of *abortion* and *birth*. This enables the president confer human features on a normally inanimate events, thereby unequivocally exemplifying contradictory words to highlight and buttress his message. In the extract, the choice of ‘abortion’ is a personified description of the wicked, selfish and unconstitutional acts of the then Military Head of state who abruptly annulled the 1993 election results, that stood out as the fairest and freest in Nigeria. On the other hand, ‘*birth*’ personifies the inspired outcome of the June 12 election results, which brought about the people’s strong insistence on the drive to have their political dreams and aspirations for an all inclusive and public participatory governance, sustained in the country. This represents the president’s attempt to deride the former Military administration, in preference for today’s democracy in Nigeria, which enhances good governance and provide efficient leadership.

The above discussions have shown that President Tinubu’s use of figurative language in his first democracy speech, creates images in the minds of the readers/listeners. They also create meaning, thereby articulating his ideas and visions. Through the employment of figurative language, the president has succeeded in contextualizing English in his speech, aimed at making the message well understood.

c. Lexical Neologism and Allusions

Also found foregrounded in the President’s speech, are concepts of neologisms and allusions, taken from the fields of geography, politics and religion. This is done in order to convey the exact communicative intention of the speaker. Thus President Tinubu produces the following expressions to create a vivid picture of the prevalent political environment in Nigeria, so as to make the message clearly understood.

Extract 6

- i. Transition from military dictatorship to a **representative government** of the people (item 2)
- ii. We celebrate a day that has remained a **watershed** in our nation’s history silver platter (item 6).
- iii. ... the **sacrifice and martyrdom** of Chief MKO Abiola (item7).
- iv. **Sacred rituals** of our democracy (item 11)
- v. May **God** continue to bless the Federal Republic of Nigeria (item25).

In the extract above, sample i (**representative government**), is the president’s coinage to describe his preference for inclusive administration (democracy), which Nigerians desired and fought to have. The use of **watershed** (ii), which is a geographical term, signifies a turning point, a significant moment of change in the political growth of Nigeria, which calls for celebration.

However, the president uses the instrumentality of the speech to succinctly put it on record that the success achieved in attaining the level of democracy Nigerians enjoy today, is not without some individuals’ efforts, commitments and deaths. Some religious lexical items foregrounded in

the speech are used to convey these investments as follows: **sacrifice, martyrdom and Sacred rituals.**

Similarly, in sample v, the deployment of “May **God** continue to bless the Federal Republic of Nigeria”, is a familiar religious expression found in the lexical registers of African Traditional Religion and Christian practice. In that context, it performs the functions of appealing to the super natural being for the release of natural blessings on this country, while desiring the greatness of the country.

d. Parallelism/Repetition

Ketanji Yankson defines parallelism as the use of pattern repetition in a literary text for a particular artistic effect (14). This suggests that parallelism occurs when some structures exhibit similarity or identical patterns. In this case, it is the similarity of the pattern that results in parallel presentation of contrast, opposition or certain levels of emphasis. Udofot and Bassey posit that when words or word groups perform the same function in the context of use, we say they are in parallel form (206).

The speech of President Tinubu is replete with some features of parallel structure, suggestive of relationships. The following expressions in his speech expose the style of his language.

Extract 7

- i.** Fellow Nigerians, (item 1).
- ii.** Fellow compatriots,(item 6)
- iii.**... I have asked you, my compatriots ... (item19)
- iv.**the struggle to de-annul the election signified their fierce commitment to enthroning democracy... The fierce opposition to the annulment...pro-democracy onslaught... equivalent of the battle against colonial rule...(item 4).
- v.** ... while in the trenches fighting on the side of the people ... the heroes of our independence struggle (item 8)

In samples i, ii and iii of the above extract, the president’s choice of “**Fellow Nigerians**” and “**compatriots**” exemplifies foregrounded feature of lexical repetition. The feature reflects the President’s use of liberal rhetorical device for the purpose of convincing his listeners. The expressions also serve as transitional devices strategically distributed in the speech to appeal to the collective sense of the people. The liberal style is adopted to woo and lure the people into the ideologies and policies of the speaker, and to cajole them into accepting his government’s proposed programmes, in order to paint the picture of the dividends of democracy in Nigeria.

Also, through the employment of parallel structures in samples iv and v, President Tinubu captures the anger stakeholders vent against the tyrannical attitude of terminating the well acclaimed results of the 1993 election, as follows: “**struggle to de-annul the election**”, “**fierce commitment to enthroning democracy**”, “**The fierce opposition to the annulment**”, “**pro-democracy onslaught**” and “**the battle against colonial rule**”. These expressions represent instances of parallelism that reveal heightened negative emotions colonial rule and military dictatorship have caused the country for many years.

Conclusion

It is obvious from the analysis of the President's Democracy Day Speech given in this study, that the language is more often than not exhibiting some foregrounded features which make it educating, enlightening and interesting. Besides, it is generally felt as it has already been established that language and politics are intertwined and inseparable. This is usually explored by the political class to grasp power and to consolidate it. Towards wooing and luring the people to cooperate, the president uses language to achieve his political intentions and goals. Our findings reveal that the speaker has used his Democracy Day Speech to perform his communicative intention, through the use of graphological features, figurative language, parallelism and neologisms in order to achieve a distinct style.

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